

Synthesis, spectral characterization and reactivity of chloro diphenyltin(IV) dithiocomplexes having Sn-S bonds

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The chloro diphenyltin(IV) complexes with the composition $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}]$ and $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)POGO\}]$ ($R = C_2H_5$; $G = -CH_2C(H)CH_3, -CH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2-$) have been prepared by the reaction of diphenyltin(IV) dichloride with NH_4 salt of *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate in absolute methanol at room temperature. The complexes have been characterized by their analytical data, IR, 1H and ^{31}P NMR spectra. Lewis base character of the complexes has been established by reacting them with Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ag^I salts. The heterobimetallic adducts are formed through the coordination of the sulfur atom of chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate to the soft metal acceptor.

Due to pronounced catalytic¹ and biological activity^{2,3} of organotin compounds and favorable environmental and toxicological properties, research interest in this area continues to be pursued actively. The reactivity of metal dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates towards soft Lewis acid are little explored⁴. In continuation of our studies on synthesis and reactivity of organometal *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates as Lewis acid and base⁵, the present paper deals with the synthesis, spectral characterization and ligation behavior of some chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate towards soft metal acceptor such as Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ag^I .

Experimental

Diphenyltin dichloride was prepared by established procedure⁶ and their purity was checked by chlorine analysis. *O,O'*-Dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphoric acids and their ammonium salts were prepared as before⁷. Solvent were purified and dried by standard method. Sulfur was estimated as $BaSO_4$ and metals were estimated by established methods⁸. The conductivity measurements in anhydrous DMSO were made on a Decible Conductivity meter model DC610. FTIR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} . 1H and ^{31}P NMR [CH_3OH-d_4 and $DMSO-d_6$] spectra were recorded at 300 MHz and 121.5 MHz on a Bruker DR-300 FT NMR spectrophotometer using TMS (as an internal standard) and H_3PO_4 (as an external standard) respectively.

Reaction of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_2$ with $NH_4\{S(S)POCHC(H)O-CH_3\}$:

A mixture of diphenyltin dichloride (3.42 g, 0.01 mol) and ammonium *O,O'*-propylene dithiophosphate (4.74 g,

0.01 mol) in absolute methanol was refluxed on water bath for about four hours and filtered. The excess solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and compound was precipitated by the addition of diethyl ether. The precipitate was filtered and washed with diethyl ether. It was dried over P_2O_5 under vacuo. The reaction of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_2$ with $NH_4\{S(S)POCH_2(CH)_3CH_2O\}$ and $NH_4\{S(S)P(OCH_2-CH_3)_2\}$ was carried out similarly.

Preparation of heterobimetallic complexes :

In a representative experiment, to a solution of chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-diethyl dithiophosphate (0.492 g, 0.001 mol) in absolute methanol (10 mL), $Hg(OCOFCF_3)_2$ (0.426 g, 0.001 mol) in same solvent (10 mL) was added and stirred at room temperature for four hours. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with methanol and finally with diethyl ether. The product was dried over P_2O_5 under vacuo.

Similar products were prepared using $Hg(SCN)_2$, $HgCl_2$, CdI_2 , $AgSCN$ and $AgOCOFCF_3$ as acceptors with all chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate.

Results and discussion

The interaction of diphenyltin dichloride with ammonium salt of corresponding *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate (1 : 1 molar ratio) in absolute methanol yields the desired product.

The 1 : 1 heterobimetallic adducts of chloro diphenyltin

Table 1. Analytical data of chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate

Sl. no.	Comps.	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis(%) : Found (Calcd.)	
					Sn	S
1.	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ Sn(Cl)S(S)P(OCH ₂ CH ₃) ₂]	White	240	82	24.14 (24.02)	12.82 (12.94)
2.	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ Sn(Cl)S(S)POCH ₂ (CH ₂) ₃ CH ₂ O]	White	166 (d)	84	23.32 (23.44)	12.51 (12.64)
3.	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ Sn(Cl)S(S)POCH ₂ (CH)OCH ₃]	White	162	90	23.22 (23.30)	12.68 (12.56)

Table 2. Analytical data of [(C₆H₅)₂Sn(Cl)S(S)P(OCH₂CH₃)₂]. M'Y or M''Y₂

Sl. no.	M'Y or M''Y ₂	Colour	Decom. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
					Sn	Cd	Hg	Ag	S
1.	HgCl ₂ [C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ S ₂ PSnCl ₃ Hg]	Grey	136	82	15.37 (15.49)	-	26.26 (26.18)	-	8.19 (8.35)
2.	CdI ₂ [C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ S ₂ PClSnCdI ₂]	Yellow	230	78	13.91 (13.79)	13.15 (13.06)	-	-	7.26 (7.43)
3.	Hg(OCOFCF ₃) ₂ [C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆ S ₂ PClSnF ₆ Hg]	Yellow	210	80	12.79 (12.88)	-	21.85 (21.77)	-	6.71 (6.94)
4.	Hg(SCN) ₂ [C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ S ₄ PClSnN ₂ Hg]	Grey	180	77	14.55 (14.63)	-	24.61 (24.73)	-	15.91 (15.78)
5.	AgSCN [C ₁₇ H ₂₀ O ₂ S ₃ PClSnNAg]	Grey	200	76	17.84 (17.97)	-	-	16.21 (16.33)	14.67 (14.53)
6.	AgOCOFCF ₃ [C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ S ₂ PClSnF ₃ Ag]	White	220	78	16.51 (16.59)	-	-	15.19 (15.07)	8.80 (8.94)

O,O'-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate with soft Lewis acceptors such as Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ag^I have been obtained by stirring a mixture of the two component in absolute methanol at room temperature.

M' = Ag; Y = SCN, OCOFCF₃;

M'' = Hg; Y = Cl, SCN, OCOFCF₃

M'' = Cd; Y = I

The analytical data (Table 1) of the chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate indicate 1 : 1 [(C₆H₅)₂SnCl : dithiophosphate] stoichiometry. The product are white solid, stable at room temperature and are not affected by the atmospheric oxygen and moisture. They are soluble in common organic solvents. The analytical data for the heterobimetallic adducts (Table 2) correspond to 1 : 1 (donor : acceptor) stoichiometry. They are solid, stable at room temperature and insoluble in common organic solvents but dissolve in DMSO. The molar conductance data (2.46–4.53 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in DMSO of chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate and their adducts indicate their non electrolytic nature and absence of ionic species in solution.

IR spectra :

IR bands observed at 1016 ± 2 and 960 ± 2 cm⁻¹ are assigned to [ν(P)-O-C] and [νP-O-(C)] stretching modes of vibration respectively. The bands at 650 ± 2 (νP=S) and 515 ± 2 (νP-S) cm⁻¹ invariably indicates the presence of unidentate *O,O'*-dialkyl dithiophosphate bonded to a chloro diphenyltin moiety⁵⁻⁹. However, in case of chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-alkylene dithiophosphate, IR bands are appeared at 1020 ± 4 [ν(P)-O-C], 972 ± 2 [νP-O-(C)], 691 ± 2 (νP=S) and 520 ± 2 (νP-S) cm⁻¹ respectively. A weak intensity band is observed at 410 ± 2 (νSn-S) cm⁻¹ (Ref. 10).

In the spectra of chloro diphenyltin *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates. M'Y or M''Y₂, the (νP=S) absorption invariably shifts from 650 ± 2 cm⁻¹ in parent dithiophosphate to 630 ± 2 cm⁻¹ (in case of diethyl dithiophosphate) in the heterobimetallic complexes. However, in case of alkylene dithiophosphate, νP=S absorption shifts from 691 ± 2 to 652 ± 2 cm⁻¹. νP-S and νSn-S remain almost unaffected in heterobimetallic complexes. The considerable lowering of νP=S indicates co-ordination from both the sulfur atoms of the ligand to the tin and soft metal acceptor. There is a drift of electron density from oxygen and carbon through phosphorus and sulfur to the soft metal atom. One

of the sulfur atom of unidentate dithiophosphate group is now attached to chloro diphenyltin and the other is coordinated to soft metal, giving rise to a bridging structure. A small positive shift in $[v(P)-O-C]$ (1028 ± 2) and $[v(P-O-C)]$ (969 ± 4) cm^{-1} (in case of diethyl dithiophosphate) and at 1030 ± 4 and 991 ± 3 cm^{-1} (in case of alkylene dithiophosphate) respectively, also indicates that on coordination from sulfur to soft metal acceptor, the considerable shift of electron density increases the bond order of C-O and P-O bonds⁵. The trifluoroacetate group are unidentate⁵ since $\nu_{\text{asy}} \text{OCO}$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{OCO}$ appear at 1680 ± 5 and 1420 ± 5 cm^{-1} , respectively with $\Delta \text{OCO} = 260 \pm 10$ cm^{-1} . The thiocyanate group is S-bonded⁵ since $\nu \text{C}=\text{N}$, $\nu \text{C}=\text{S}$ and νNCS bands appears at ~ 2080 , ~ 720 and ~ 440 cm^{-1} respectively. Absorption due to Hg-Cl and Cd-I stretching modes could not be identified as they lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

¹H NMR spectra : ¹H NMR spectra of $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2\}]$, the C_6H_5 -Sn, O-CH₂ and CH₃ signals appear at δ 7.88–7.41 (m), 4.02–3.94 (m) and 1.27–1.22 (t) ppm respectively. In the spectra of $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2\}]\cdot\text{HgCl}_2$, C_6H_5 -Sn signals appear at δ 7.87–7.32 (m), whereas there is slight low field shift in O-CH₂ and CH₃ protons which emerge at δ 4.05–3.97 (m) and 1.32–1.25 (t) ppm respectively. The positions and integration of the peaks are consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of the complexes. The low field shift of alkyl protons in heterobimetallic complexes indicate considerable shift of electron density from oxygen to the soft metal acceptor through sulfur⁵.

³¹P NMR spectra : In the ³¹P NMR (proton decoupled) spectra of $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2]$, a single peak is observed at δ 109.77 ppm which is in agreement with the earlier report for a four-coordinated tin atom in dithiophosphate derivatives¹¹. However, the ³¹P NMR spectra of $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Cl})\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2]\cdot\text{AgOCOCF}_3$ show deshielding of the phosphorus atom to the extent of about δ 1.6 ppm from the parent triphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-diethyl dithiophosphate and a peak at δ 111.37 ppm is observed. The deshielding of the phosphorus atom in heterobimetallic complexes supports the finding of IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

On the basis of above analytical and spectral (IR, ¹H and ³¹P NMR) evidences and support from the previous work¹², a tetrahedral structure containing a unidentate dithiophosphate group and a four coordinated tin atom may be assigned to chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate. Moreover, in case of heterobimetallic

complexes, it is assumed that two molecules of metal acceptors are bind to two different sulfur atom. The dithiophosphate groups thus act as a bridge between chloro diphenyltin and soft metal and the following structures may be proposed for chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate. M'Y or M''Y₂.

In these heterobimetallic complexes, Hg^{II} and Cd^{II} are tricoordinated and Ag^I possess a coordination number of two¹³.

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